

Plankton functional type models

Milestone 10 – Part 1 (Arctic)

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POMP Milestone 10 Plankton Functional Type models

29 January 2026

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New descriptions of plankton functional types (PFTs: *Phaeocystis*, heavily silicifying diatoms) were developed and implemented into the ocean biogeochemistry model FESOM-REcoM. Code and data are available, the code is considered final, data is being worked with and will be deposited once publications are finalized.

Part 1: Implementation of Phaeocystis (PhD student Sina Müller)

Code:

- Ocean biogeochemical model code including phaeocystis (FESOM2.1-REcoM3):
https://github.com/FESOM/fesom2/tree/fesom2_4phy_temp
- Results are presented as trend maps of NPP and carbon export (see Figure 1 and 2 below, also e.g.):
https://github.com/mueller79/transient_analysis_masterthesis/blob/main/transient_analysis_SM/trend_maps.ipynb

Phaeocystis implementation:

An additional PFT '*Phaeocystis*' that is thought to become increasingly prominent in the future Arctic Ocean was implemented for the polar regions in the biogeochemical model FESOM2.1-REcoM. To do so, a new temperature function was derived specifically for polar *Phaeocystis* species from observational data. Furthermore, the model was tuned for the *Phaeocystis* growth dependencies on CO₂, light and nutrients. The model was evaluated with observational data and a hindcast simulation was performed from 1958 to 2023 (Figure 1). Using the output of this run, the trends of the net primary production (NPP) of the phytoplankton, the carbon export (C-export) and the shift in the phytoplankton community composition in the Arctic Ocean was analyzed over the period from 1970 to 2023 using the scripts 'trend_maps.ipynb' (Figure 2 and 3). The results were reported in a master's thesis and presented as a poster at the Polar Marine Science in Lucca, Italy in March 2025. After this, the model was further developed and coupled to the most recent FESOM version – 2.7 that will be used for further analysis such as future projections of NPP in the Arctic Ocean.

Fig. 1: Global distribution of phytoplankton biomass (Diatoms – top left, Small Phytoplankton – top right, Coccolithophores – bottom left and newly implemented polar Phaeocystis spp – bottom right). Obtained from FESOM2.1-REcoM3 model output; integrated over upper 100 meters.

Fig. 2: Absolute changes of net primary production (NPP) of four phytoplankton functional types (A – Small Phytoplankton, B – Diatoms, C – Coccolithophores and D – Phaeocystis) over time period from 1970 to 2023 and evaluation of the sea-ice extent.

Fig. 3: Relative changes of NPP (A) and carbon export flux at 30 m (B) over time period from 1970 to 2023 and evaluation of the sea-ice extent.

